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BB-5102 ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR

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Title:

Reflective Report

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Background

In the context of learning, some authors describe it as a career which is not necessarily linear: Individuals seem to learn some in one area, move on to another, return to what they've learned before and revised and refine it, probably building on what they've learned in other areas (Swain and Hammond, 2011). As a part-time and mature student taking a Masters in Management, I could probably relate myself to that statement. I've graduated with my undergrads (BA in Professional Communication & the Media) in the year 2016 and prior to that, I was working for four years with Bank Islam Brunei Darussalam as a Personal Banker. Moving forward to 2017, I've started working with a local SME (Repathlete) as a Marketing & Promotional officer. Moreover, during the mini lockdown in May, I had found the opportunity to open up a coffee shop (Bicara) back home in Seria while working from home (WFH). It is an interesting year for me so far despite the pandemic of covid-19. It is because around the same time I also received an offer letter for Masters which I would consider it to be part of my self-fulfilment. In other words, I am juggling a startup company, marketing for Repathlete and pursuing my dream to attain a Master degree.

Planning Phase

As I mentioned, I had graduated in 2016, since then I've never written any paper for assignment or work. Hence, I have had a tough time doing a report in my first short paper on a case study. Furthermore, online class probably not a good idea to begin the course especially for an individual who had been out from the academic environment for so long. Additionally, coming in from different faculty is another challenge for myself. The structure and framework for the assignment/paper are somehow different from my undergrads.

We were assigned two tasks, Individual and Group work. There are a few challenges that I encountered during the group task. Firstly, finding a group was tough where we had to get into a group online. Thankfully, I have managed to find a group that needs an additional member for a complete team. Secondly, I had to juggle two jobs which are both important to me especially to my start-up business which at that time, I still had to create and adjust my business model. Hence, group discussion was a bit of difficulty as well due to my day jobs. Therefore, most group discussions were online. Thirdly, overwhelm tasks from this and other modules was also a challenge.

Executing Phase

Moving on to the project, we chose Social Loafing as our group work. Our main project goals were to have a solid paper regarding social loafing in Brunei. Our project plan was to do readings on previous work relating to the topic. Next, we to prepare a questionnaire to local universities for a survey based on the paper. And, our plan was to gather all the information acquired and discuss it among ourself. This activity definitely boarder our skills because most of the requirements are new to us.

We assigned ourself and gathered journals from reliable sources. Due to time constraints, we did most of our communication online. However, we did encounter a few problems while trying to access the journals. As I mentioned above, the gathering of information and resources are different comparing from past experience. It took a while for myself to get into the process of learning or writing for the paper. Additionally, while waiting for the approval for consent letter, we had distributed our survey via online due to the pandemic that is happening at the moment. We received all the responses and we breakdown the information received. We were also planning to do some interviews regarding social loafing amongst university students.

Challenges

However, we hit a few more challenges ahead. Our consent letter for interviewing was rejected due to some internal difficulties. The outcome made us changed the scoop of the paper into another dimension. Hence, it was like making a new paper with only a few weeks to spare. We did panic thinking whether we have enough time to finish the paper. What changed the paper to *A Systematic Literature Review: Social Loafing and Impact of Group Diversity on Group Performance* where we used some research from countries like the US, South Korea, Germany, UK, Taiwan and Singapore and try to relate it with Brunei. As for our theoretical framework, we used social impact theory, social exchange theory and moral disengagement theory. Furthermore, at the end of the deadline, one of our members had to pull out from the courses due to a job offered that was given to her. She did put a lot into the paper and it was mixed emotion to know that she had to leave at the very end of the paper. However, we pushed through and managed to get it done a few days before the deadline.

The outcome of the project

To sum all up, the team had great communication and understanding of each other. They helped myself to get back into academic writing skill even if I feel I could have done better if I had better time management skills to juggle Master with two professions. Additionally, we would discuss which part that each of us should focus more individually. With their help, I personally feel it made my transition from not being in an academic environment into challenging online course smoother. From this group project, it shows a lot of my weakness which I need to work on soon especially on mapping the paper and time management. However, I personally think my strength is at my communication skills where I believe I could blend into a group in a casual manner. I would also believe that I am bringing in a different perspective through and from mature student to the group project.

Suggestions

Overall, I personally believe that the final project was good enough despite the challenges that we faced along the way. However, there are few suggestions that I feel we as a group could improve the work. Firstly, a face-to-face meeting and discussion are important in starting up the project where I think that we did not have a proper structure and timeline prior to doing the project. Secondly, we should be more specific in assigning tasks. Some tasks were unclear as we had a hard time communicating with the requirements needed by the lecturer. And lastly, we should have been more aware of the deadline as most of our work was done close to the end.

On the other hand, I personally think that the project could have been better if I have managed my time properly. As a part-time student, I really need to schedule everything around my business and job. This is because I believe that my new start-up is probably one of my top priority at the moment. Additionally, Brunei has a society that has a small culture of entrepreneurship and a culture of risk aversion towards employability (Musa and Idris, 2020). Hence, I would hope to inspire the youths to be involved in entrepreneurship and be more of a risk-taker. However, this course is definitely as important as my start-up in which it could help not only the business but for me in the future. Therefore, I would have to assign a particular day or time just for university work and probably take fewer modules in a semester.

Conclusion

In conclusion, with this reflective reports, I manage to identify my strengths and weaknesses on this semester that I need to work on for future project as it creates self-awareness.

Self-awareness includes an appreciation of one's abilities, shortcomings, and limits, how knowledge is gathered and stored, how uncertain and stressful circumstances are treated, and how it is interpreted and interacted with others (Musa and Idris, 2020). Hence, this reflective report is beneficial for my future needs.

References:

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